

OPTIMIZING DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, AND IMPROVING QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH COMBINED MAXILLOFACIAL TRAUMA

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the historical development of maxillofacial surgery worldwide and discusses aspects of combined craniocerebral trauma. It also explores modern surgical methods for the treatment of combined maxillofacial trauma. A differentiated approach to the treatment of combined maxillofacial trauma is explored. Quality of life and pain are assessed using questionnaires. Determining the effectiveness of surgical treatment and its impact on patients' quality of life.

Relevance. According to international literature, since the beginning of the 21st century, there has been a steady increase in maxillofacial trauma both in Russia and in Europe and North America. According to several authors, the proportion of maxillofacial injuries among all bone injuries ranges from 3.2 to 11%, with facial bone fractures occurring in 88.2%, soft tissue injuries in 9.9%, and facial burns in 1.9%. In the United States alone, traumatic brain injury occurs in 1.6 million victims, 260,000 of whom are hospitalized, 60,000 die, and 85,000 are assigned disability. Severe TBI includes two discrete, distinct types: primary and secondary. Acute traumatic brain injury is characterized by unpredictable consequences. No one can accurately predict the outcome of the disease, even in its mildest form. Acute traumatic brain injury attracts the attention of researchers due to its high mortality rate in the early stages and frequent disability in the residual period. Due to neurological defects and resulting personality changes, victims are unable to adapt to life, and social adaptation suffers. The diversity of damaging factors and injuries complicates the creation of a unified classification that can satisfy all researchers and clinicians. Therefore, improving the working classification of zygomatic orbital complex injuries is of great theoretical and practical interest.

Diagnosis and treatment of traumatic injuries to the upper face remain one of the most challenging issues in modern emergency surgery. The introduction of modern diagnostic methods such as multislice computed tomography (MSCT) with the ability to subsequently process the obtained data to generate multiplanar reconstruction (MPR) and 3D reconstruction images has increased the sensitivity and accuracy of craniofacial fracture detection, enabling a more detailed analysis of traumatic orbital injuries. Quality of life assessment is increasingly being used in clinical medicine because it allows us to study the impact of disease on various components of a patient's health and identify additional benefits or drawbacks of treatment. The introduction of advanced quality of life assessment methods

into clinical practice has provided access to important information about aspects of patient functioning. This data can be used to develop treatment and rehabilitation programs and monitor the patient's condition during treatment. Thus, the alarming increase in the incidence and consequences of acute traumatic brain injury make it a serious social problem of national significance.

The goal is to improve treatment outcomes for patients with concomitant maxillofacial trauma by using modern methods of comprehensive diagnostics, differentiated treatment strategies, and quality of life assessment.

Material and Methods. We analyzed data from 234 patients with combined maxillofacial injuries treated in the Maxillofacial Surgery Department of the Tashkent State Dental Institute, Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, between 2019 and 2024. Our differentiated approach to treatment tactics, conservative and surgical treatment, was based on the clinical presentation, objective instrumental examination findings, the severity of neurological signs, and assessment of patient consciousness using the Glasgow Coma Scale and other methods. To assess quality of life, we used the EuroQol-5D European Quality of Life Questionnaire and the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) to determine pain intensity, both of which had undergone a standard validation procedure. After diagnosis, all patients underwent surgery, including colostomy, various anastomoses, and other reconstructive procedures.

Results and Discussion. All 234 patients with combined maxillofacial trauma were divided into two groups based on the severity of the injury. The first group included 104 (44.4%) patients with moderate-severity injuries who received conservative treatment of the lower maxillofacial region and moderate brain contusions. The second group included 130 (55.5%) patients with severe injuries and severe brain contusions who primarily underwent surgical treatment of the lower and middle maxillofacial region. In our study, all 234 patients were classified by gender and age group according to the World Health Organization classification. Our differentiated approach to tactics, conservative and surgical treatment, was based on the clinical presentation, objective instrumental examination findings, and patient age and gender assessment. It should be noted that patients often sustained injuries at home due to falls from low heights: in the bathroom, from a chair, sofa, bed, cot, windowsill, down the stairs, or while riding a bicycle. In the first group of patients with combined maxillofacial trauma, the overwhelming majority of the time (60.7%), the primary cause of injury was a fall from standing height, with 61.1% of patients also suffering from injuries sustained as a result of falls, 12.4% from criminal trauma, and 15.4% from road traffic accidents.

Conclusions. Depending on the clinical phase of the disease, patients with combined maxillofacial trauma were divided as follows: 128 (54.7%) patients were in the clinical compensation stage; 64 (27.3%) were in the clinical subcompensation stage; 33 (14.1%) were in the moderate clinical decompensation stage; 9 (3.9%) were in the clinical decompensation stage. According to the obtained data of our study, a significant part of patients with combined maxillofacial trauma were men of working age 184 (78.6%), which is a pressing problem both in social and economic aspects. When examining the somatic status, it was revealed that among 234 patients, 94 (40.2%) had somatic pathology, manifested in the form of arterial hypertension in 30 (31.9%), neurological pathology 31 (32.9%), ischemic heart disease in 7 (7.4%) cases. In 7 (7.4%) observations, gastroenterology, ENT organs 7 (7.4%),

endocrinology in 7 (7.4%), oncology 3 (3.2%), ophthalmology 2 (2.1%) patients liver pathology and 1 (1.1%) renal failure. An analysis of the obtained study data across groups of 234 patients with maxillofacial fractures revealed the following number of cases: 456 (100%), mandible fractures, 362 (79.4%), zygomatic bone fractures (66 (14.5%), maxilla fractures (16 (3.5%)), and nasal bone fractures (12 (2.6%)), which is very relevant.

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